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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“LOVE WAITS LIKE A DOG”

Forever faithful, forever true
We wait and watch, with hearts that bruise.
Like loyal dogs, we sit and stay
Hoping that someday, love will find its way.

Our eyes grow dim, our hearts grow old,
As seasons pass, yet love remains untold.
We whine and whimper, in the dark of night
As the ache within us, becomes a hollow light.

We'll sit and wait, through every stormy night
With every moment, our hearts will hold on tight.
To the hope that someday, love will hear our plea
And rescue us, from this endless misery.

But as the years go by, and love doesn't arrive
We're left with nothing, but a deep and endless sigh.
Our tails that once wagged, with hope and delight
Now hang limp and still, in the dark of night.

And when at last, our weary eyes grow dim
And our hearts give out, from the weight of waiting within.
We'll lay our heads down, in the dust and the pain
And whisper our final prayer, for a love that never came.